

**ПРОГНОСТИЧНА ЦІННІСТЬ ТОПОІЗОМЕРАЗИ 2 АЛЬФА У
ПАЦІЄНТІВ З ТРИЧІ НЕГАТИВНИМ РАКОМ МОЛОЧНОЇ ЗАЛОЗИ**

**PREDICATIVE SIGNIFICANCE OF TOPOISOMERASE 2 ALPHA
IN PATIENTS WITH TRIPLE-NEGATIVE BREAST CANCER**

Самусєва А. А.¹, Пономарьова О. В.^{1,2}, Зайчук В. В.³

Samusieva A.¹, Ponomarova O.^{1,2}, Zaichuk V.³

¹ORCID: 0000-0003-2222-1683

²ORCID: 0000-0002-2466-3277

³ORCID: 0000-0001-9311-7221

¹Національний університет охорони здоров'я України імені П. Л. Шупика,
кафедра онкології, Київ, Україна

²Київський міський клінічний онкологічний центр, Київ, Україна

³Національний медичний університет імені О. О. Богомольця, Київ, Україна

¹Shupyk National Healthcare University of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine

²Kyiv Municipal Clinical Oncological Center, Kyiv, Ukraine

³Bogomolets National Medical University, Kyiv, Ukraine

Науковий керівник: к. мед. н. доцент кафедри онкології **Пономарьова О. В.**

Scientific supervisor: Associate Professor of Department of Oncology, PhD

О. Ponomarova

Національний університет охорони здоров'я України імені П. Л. Шупика

Кафедра онкології

м. Київ, Україна

Shupyk National Healthcare University of Ukraine

Department of Oncology

Kyiv, Ukraine

e-mail: a_samusieva@yahoo.com

Introduction. More than 2 million new cases of breast cancer (BC) are registered annually. BC is the most common malignant disease among women, both in Ukraine and in the world. Triple-negative (TN) BC is a group of carcinomas where the expression of estrogen receptors (ER), progesterone receptors (PR), and overexpression of the HER2 receptor is absent making it the most problematic subtype of BC. Among all cases of BC, TNBC occurs in about 15% of cases and has a number of characteristic features: frequent occurrence in young women, rapid growth, and weak correlation between the size of the primary tumor and survival. The combination of clinical, pathomorphological, and molecular data allows us to predict the course of the disease and optimize treatment tactics. In TNBC, traditional targets (ER, PR, and HER2 receptors) for the treatment are missing, so the research of prognostically valuable markers remains promising, which allows for optimization treatment in such cases.

The aim. To determine the effect of topoisomerase 2 alpha (TOP2 alpha) on the course of TNBC.

Materials and methods. The study involved 38 patients with TNBC. The average age at the time of detection of breast cancer in the group was 52.6 ± 11.8 years (from 26 to 74 years) and they were diagnosed with TNBC stage II and III. All tumors were verified pathomorphologically and expression levels of ER, PR, HER2, Ki67, and TOP2 alpha were determined by immunohistochemistry analysis. Patients were divided into 2 groups:

Group 1 - patients with the level of expression of TOP2 alpha $<45\%$ - 55.3% (n = 21);

Group 2 - patients with the expression level of TOP2 alpha $>46\%$ - 44.7% (n = 17).

All patients in the study received neoadjuvant chemotherapy in accordance with the standards of treatment of BC. Evaluation of ER, PR, HER2, Ki67, and TOP2 alpha before neoadjuvant chemotherapy was performed from core biopsy material and from surgical material after neoadjuvant chemotherapy.

Results. During the analysis, there was discovered no correlation between TOP 2 alpha before neoadjuvant chemotherapy performed to Ki67 before neoadjuvant chemotherapy ($p = 0,359$). The higher ($p=0,047$) expression of TOP2 alpha before neoadjuvant chemotherapy was found in patients with moderately differentiated carcinomas compared to patients with poor and undifferentiated carcinomas. Pathological response of 3rd and 4th degrees reached 43.7% (7) in patients from group 1 and 47.4% (9) in patients from group 2. There was also a decrease of ($p = 0,001$) risk of mastectomy for taxane-based neoadjuvant chemotherapy regimens compared to non-taxane-based neoadjuvant chemotherapy regimens. Breast-sparing operations were performed for 58.8% (10) patients from group 1 and for 42.9% (9) patients from group 2. There was a decrease ($p = 0,040$) in the risk of recurrence with increasing levels of TOP2 alpha before neoadjuvant chemotherapy and a decrease ($p = 0,017$) in the risk of recurrence for patients with an increasing number of courses of adjuvant chemotherapy. The results of our research show that TOP2 alpha is a marker that may have prognostic value alone or in combination with others and allows for optimizing the treatment of patients with TNBC.